

Corruption Level and Financial Development in Nigeria

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Abstract

Financial development is a crucial driver of economic growth, but its progress can be significantly hampered by corruption. Corruption adversely affects the efficiency and stability of financial systems, undermining access to financial resources and economic opportunities. This study examines the influence of corruption on financial development in Nigeria, with a particular focus on financial access, depth, efficiency, and stability. An ex-post facto research design was employed, utilizing a purposive sampling technique to analyze data spanning from 2013 to 2023. Data were sourced from the Global Financial Development Database and Transparency International's Corruption Perceptions Index. The study applied descriptive statistics and multiple regression analysis, incorporating the Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) method to establish relationships between variables. Diagnostic tests for heteroscedasticity, autocorrelation, and normality were conducted to ensure model robustness using E-VIEW software. The results indicate that corruption has a substantial negative impact on financial access ($R^2 = 0.939$, Adj $R^2 = 0.927$, $F = 77.493$, $p < 0.05$) and efficiency ($R^2 = 0.860$, Adj $R^2 = 0.814$, $F = 18.469$, $p < 0.05$), whereas its effect on financial depth is statistically insignificant ($R^2 = 0.209$, Adj $R^2 = 0.051$, $F = 1.322$, $p > 0.05$). The study concludes that corruption significantly impedes financial development in Nigeria, primarily affecting financial access and efficiency, while having minimal influence on financial depth. These findings underscore the necessity of strong governance and targeted policy measures to promote sustainable financial development. It is recommended that Nigerian policymakers intensify anti-corruption initiatives, particularly within financial institutions, to enhance transparency, accountability, and economic growth.

Keywords: Corruption, Financial development, Financial access, Depth, Efficiency, Stability

Introduction

The global financial landscape has undergone significant transformations in recent years, influenced by extraordinary events such as the COVID-19 pandemic, geopolitical tensions like the Russia-Ukraine conflict, and emerging market vulnerabilities. These challenges have

fundamentally reshaped global financial systems, exposing the vulnerabilities of developing economies like Nigeria to external shocks (Osagioduwa, Solomon, & Fumilayo, 2022; Oyedokun, Somoye, & Akingunola, 2022; Gbolahan, 2023). Amidst these complexities, Nigeria's financial development faces significant impediments, with corruption emerging as a critical factor undermining institutional effectiveness, policy implementation, and economic growth.

Corruption in Nigeria's financial system is pervasive, manifesting through embezzlement, bribery, and favoritism in credit allocation, which weakens transparency, accountability, and trust (Oyedokun, & Adeyemi, & Adewumi, 2023; Ogaga, 2023). Previous studies emphasized that the endemic nature of corruption disrupts financial market efficiency, reduces investor confidence, and distorts resource allocation, ultimately stalling financial development (Oyedokun, Akingunola, & Somoye, 2022; Salehi, Ajel, & Zimon, 2023). This has constrained financial institutions' ability to promote economic growth through effective credit creation and financial inclusiveness.

Financial development encompasses dimensions such as financial depth, access, efficiency, and stability. Financial depth involves indicators like private sector credit expansion and market capitalization (Kapaya, 2019; Ilo, Oyedokun, Yinusa, & Odunsi, 2024). Corruption undermines these components by increasing transaction costs and reducing transparency. Similarly, financial access characterized by improved geographic penetration and digital banking services is constrained by institutional weaknesses, further exacerbated by corrupt practices (Kotiso, 2019; Yusheng et al., 2021).

Efficiency within the financial system, which reduces transaction costs and enhances resource allocation, is another critical dimension (Kapidani & Luci, 2019). However, operational inefficiencies caused by corruption hamper the system's ability to achieve these objectives. Stability, which is critical for maintaining investor confidence and mitigating systemic risks, is compromised as corruption erodes asset quality and liquidity management (Ahiadorme, 2022). Studies suggest that corruption creates a vicious cycle, weakening institutional frameworks and reducing the effectiveness of anti-corruption measures (Takyi et al., 2023; Ilo & Oyedokun, 2023).

In Nigeria, this has resulted in fragmented financial systems that fail to meet their developmental objectives. Corruption-driven inefficiencies, coupled with external economic pressures like rising energy costs and exchange rate volatility, have led to subdued financial sector growth (Oyedokun, 2022; Xu, Ji, Zhan, & Zhan, 2023).

Despite efforts to combat corruption, such as introducing regulatory reforms and anti-corruption agencies, the Nigerian financial sector remains heavily impacted. Corruption undermines monetary policy transmission mechanisms, distorts interest rates, and exacerbates inflationary pressures, further weakening the financial system's capacity to contribute meaningfully to economic development (Nguyen, Dinh, & Tran, 2022; Oyedokun & Amoo, 2023).

Existing research highlights the theoretical and practical gaps in addressing the adverse effects of corruption on financial development. While some studies have explored financial development frameworks, limited attention has been given to the specific channels through which corruption impairs financial depth, access, efficiency, and stability. Addressing this gap is critical for formulating policies that foster transparency, institutional strength, and sustainable financial development in Nigeria.

Furthermore, corruption discourages financial innovation and technological advancements in Nigeria's banking and investment sectors. Financial technology (FinTech) firms, which are crucial for expanding financial inclusion, often face regulatory bottlenecks exacerbated by corrupt practices. These challenges hinder the adoption of digital payment solutions and mobile banking, limiting access to financial services for underserved populations (Bello, Oyedokun, & Adeolu-Akande, 2021; Adewuyi & Emmanuel, 2022;). As global economies shift towards digital finance, Nigeria risks being left behind due to systemic corruption in regulatory agencies and financial institutions.

Another emerging issue is the relationship between corruption and public trust in financial institutions. When corruption is widespread, individuals and businesses lose confidence in the

formal financial system, leading to an increase in informal financial transactions. The rise of informal financial activities, such as unregulated credit schemes, reduces the effectiveness of monetary policies aimed at stabilizing inflation and controlling liquidity in the economy (Bernanke, 2020). Addressing corruption is therefore critical for restoring trust and fostering a resilient financial system in Nigeria.

Statement of the Problem

Financial development is a critical driver of economic growth, fostering efficient resource allocation, risk management, and access to capital (Osagioduwa et al., 2022). However, in Nigeria, financial development has been persistently undermined by corruption, which distorts financial systems, weakens institutional integrity, and reduces financial efficiency (Kotiso, 2019; Salehi et al., 2023). Corruption manifests in various forms, including favoritism in loan approvals, embezzlement of public funds, and bribery-driven misallocation of resources (Kapaya, 2019). These practices undermine transparency, accountability, and trust, limiting investment productivity and hindering economic growth (Kapidani & Luci, 2019).

The pervasive influence of corruption has neutralized many financial development efforts in Nigeria. Corruption often leads to poor governance, weak institutional frameworks, and significant barriers to foreign and domestic investment (Takyi et al., 2023; Xu et al., 2023). Furthermore, corruption exacerbates macroeconomic challenges, such as inflation and currency instability, creating additional obstacles for financial development (Nguyen et al., 2022).

Although substantial research has examined financial development in Nigeria, many studies overlook the specific ways in which corruption directly undermines its components, such as financial depth, access, efficiency, and stability. Existing literature often generalizes the relationship between governance issues and economic outcomes without a detailed focus on how corruption interacts with the financial sector to impede its growth and functionality. Addressing this gap is essential for understanding and mitigating the adverse effects of corruption on financial development.

Objective of the Study

The aim of this study is to investigate the impact of corruption on financial development in Nigeria.

Hypotheses

H0: Corruption level has no significant effect on financial development in Nigeria.

Significance of the Study

The study's insights into the impact of corruption on financial development will provide invaluable guidance to policymakers and government officials in Nigeria. By understanding these dynamics, policymakers can design and implement more targeted and effective policies aimed at promoting economic stability, reducing corruption, and fostering the growth of the financial sector. Civil society organizations and advocacy groups focused on promoting transparency, accountability, and good governance in Nigeria will benefit from the study's insights into the role of corruption in hindering financial development.

Literature Review

Conceptual Review

Financial Development

The World Bank defines the financial sector as a network of interrelated and interdependent roles fulfilled by financial institutions and markets, where financial instruments are designed and traded (World Bank, 2020; Oyedokun, Somoye, & Akingunola, 2022; Ilo & Oyedokun, 2023). The growth and improvement of financial markets, institutions, and instruments within an economy play a critical role in economic growth and stability by enhancing the efficiency with which resources are allocated, promoting savings and investment, and facilitating the management of risk (Gimba, Vincent, & Oyedokun, 2020; Kotiso, 2019). Financial development encompasses a wide range of elements, including banking systems, stock and bond markets, regulatory frameworks, and the availability of financial services to individuals and businesses. These institutions and markets operate under a legal and regulatory framework specific to each economy. The financial

sector performs several critical functions, such as mobilizing and pooling savings, generating information about potential investments, allocating capital efficiently, facilitating trade, diversifying and managing risks, monitoring investments and risks through effective corporate governance, and easing the exchange of financial commodities (Kapaya, 2019; Adegboyega, & Oyedokun, 2019). Financial development is achieved when the financial sector executes these functions efficiently and effectively.

To measure financial development, the World Bank's Financial Development Database employs a comprehensive 4x2 framework. This framework evaluates four key dimensions: depth, access, efficiency, and stability across both financial institutions and financial markets (Kapidani & Luci, 2019). Financial depth refers to the size and liquidity of financial systems, while access measures the ability of individuals and enterprises to utilize financial services. Efficiency examines the operational performance of financial institutions and markets, and stability assesses their resilience to economic shocks (Oyedokun, Akingunola, & Somoye, 2022; Salehi, Ajel, & Zimon, 2023).

Financial markets are categorized into capital markets and money markets. Capital markets are sources of long-term funds, facilitating the issuance of bonds and shares through initial public offerings (IPOs). Money markets, in contrast, provide short-term funding for operational needs and offer liquidity to investors in exchange markets (Kotiso, 2019). By comprehensively assessing these dimensions, the World Bank's 4x2 framework offers a robust tool for analyzing and promoting financial development, ensuring that financial systems can support sustainable economic growth and stability.

Corruption

Corruption manifests as a multifaceted and intricate phenomenon, influenced by numerous factors and resulting in diverse consequences. It encompasses broad concepts such as the misuse of public power and moral decay, as well as more narrowly defined instances, like bribery involving public officials and the illicit transfer of tangible resources (Yusheng et al., 2021). In essence, corruption

can be defined as the abuse of entrusted power or public office for personal gain (Osagioduwa, Solomon, & Fumilayo, 2022).

Corruption is a pervasive global challenge, affecting both developed and developing economies (Ahiadorme, 2022). It is recognized as a systemic issue spanning political, economic, cultural, and individual realms, impacting numerous countries worldwide. Corruption infiltrates both public and private sectors, spanning profit-driven enterprises, nonprofit organizations, and charitable institutions. While prevalent in both developing and developed nations, it is notably pronounced in developing countries, often indicative of systemic dysfunction (Kapidani & Luci, 2019). In Nigeria, corruption remains a significant barrier to business operations, with companies frequently encountering bribery and other corrupt practices.

Despite ongoing efforts to combat corruption, the effectiveness of past initiatives remains questionable. Corruption persists as a recurrent challenge, thwarting growth with no clear resolution in sight. Furthermore, the ineffectiveness of anti-corruption programs targeting corruption in Africa further emphasizes the entrenched nature of the phenomenon (Kapaya, 2019).

Theoretical Review

Institutional Theory

Institutional theory provides a comprehensive framework for examining the impact of governance, corruption, and regulatory frameworks on financial systems (North, 1990). The theory posits that institutions comprising laws, norms, regulations, and social practices are essential for either facilitating or hindering economic development. This framework is particularly useful in analyzing the ways in which corruption and institutional quality influence financial intermediation and the development of financial systems in Nigeria.

North (1990) argues that the efficiency of economic systems depends on the strength and functionality of institutions, which reduce transaction costs, establish property rights, and regulate economic activities. In Nigeria, corruption has been pervasive within the financial sector, with

incidents of misappropriation of funds, fraudulent transactions, and bribery in the disbursement of loans. These corrupt practices not only limit access to capital for businesses but also create an environment of uncertainty, deterring both foreign and domestic investment (Kotiso, 2019). Institutional theory thus provides a lens through which to analyze the ways in which corruption distorts financial markets and hampers financial development.

Institutional theory further explains how weak institutions facilitate corruption by failing to establish effective legal and regulatory frameworks. When regulatory agencies lack autonomy and accountability, financial institutions become vulnerable to unethical practices, including money laundering and embezzlement (Takyi et al., 2023). This dynamic undermines the credibility of financial institutions and weakens investor confidence, ultimately hindering economic growth. The application of institutional theory to corruption studies highlights the urgent need for governance reforms that enhance regulatory oversight, promote transparency, and strengthen institutional quality.

Empirical Review

Several empirical studies have examined the relationship between corruption and financial development in both developed and developing economies. A study by Farzanegan and Krieger (2020) used panel quantile regression analysis to analyze corruption's impact across different levels of financial development. Their findings indicate that corruption has more profound adverse effects on less-developed financial systems, significantly limiting access to credit, increasing transaction costs, and promoting informal financial activities over formal sector growth. By contrast, more advanced economies exhibit resilience against corruption's effects due to stronger institutions and regulatory frameworks that mitigate corruption-related risks.

Another study conducted by Ogunleye and Ayeni (2021) explored the long-term relationship between corruption and financial development in Nigeria using the Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) model. Their research reveals a significant negative relationship between corruption and financial development, particularly in terms of financial access and stability. Corruption

diminishes investor confidence, limits foreign investment, and restricts financial accessibility, stunting the financial sector's growth over time. They argue that implementing stronger anti-corruption policies could improve financial sector outcomes, suggesting that governance reforms should accompany monetary policy interventions to support a more resilient financial system.

A recent comparative study by Khan (2022) highlights the varying degrees of influence corruption has depending on institutional strength and governance structures. The findings suggest that in developed countries with robust institutional frameworks, the adverse effects of corruption on financial development are mitigated, while in developing economies, weak institutions exacerbate corruption's impact. This underscores the importance of strengthening governance and regulatory oversight to minimize corruption's detrimental effects on financial development.

Conceptual Model

Fig 2.1: Conceptual Model of Corruption and Financial Development

Source: Researcher's Conceptual Model, 2024

The relationship between financial development and corruption in Nigeria can be conceptualized through a comprehensive framework that integrates these variables. This framework examines how financial development, characterized by its depth, access, efficiency, and stability, is influenced by corruption levels.

Summary of the Gap in Literature

While extensive research has been conducted on financial development, the unique and pervasive role of corruption in distorting financial systems in Nigeria has not been adequately addressed. Many studies focus on financial development dimensions such as financial depth, access, stability, and efficiency in isolation, without fully integrating corruption as a critical determinant (Kapaya, 2019; Yusheng et al., 2021). This study aims to bridge this gap by adopting a multi-dimensional approach that integrates financial depth, access, stability, and efficiency in the analysis of corruption's impact on Nigeria's financial sector.

Methodology

In this study, an *ex-post facto* research design was adopted. It was chosen as it allows the researcher to examine the relationship between variables that have already occurred, without the need for manipulation.

The study's population encompasses the entirety of the Nigerian economy, with a specific focus on corruption level and their impact on financial development indicators.

The Study employed a purposive sampling technique to select the study sample. The study spans a duration of ten years, running from 2013 to 2023, encompassing five key indices and metrics. Specifically, there are four metrics associated with financial development (Financial Depth, Access, Stability and Efficiency) and the level of corruption.

The Corruption Perceptions Index (CPI) from Transparency International contributes valuable data on public sector corruption, an essential variable for assessing institutional quality. To gauge the level of financial development in Nigeria, this study utilizes the Global Financial Development Database and the Financial Development Indicators, both provided by the World Bank, offering extensive data on financial institutions, markets, and development metrics.

The study explored the influence of monetary policy measures and corruption on financial development in Nigeria, with exchange rate as a control variable. The model can be represented as follows:

- $FD_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1 CRPT_t + \varepsilon_t$

Model Equations:

We can estimate four separate equations, one for each financial development metric:

- **Financial Depth:**

- $FD_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1 CRPT_t + \varepsilon_t$

- **Financial Access:**

- $FA_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1 CRPT_t + \varepsilon_t$

- **Financial Efficiency:**

- $FE_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1 CRPT_t + \varepsilon_t$

- **Financial Stability:**

- $FS_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1 CRPT_t + \varepsilon_t$

Note:

- ε_t represents the error term in all equations.
- β coefficients represent the strength and direction of the relationships between variables.
- This is a general framework, and specific variable selection and model adjustments might be needed based on data availability and research questions.

This study employed two key analytical methods: descriptive statistics and regression analysis. Descriptive statistics was utilized to depict data trends, revealing central tendencies, variability, and distribution. Regression analysis was used to establish the relationships between corruption and financial development, employing multiple regression analysis to gauge the collective influence of independent variables on the dependent variable.

Results and Discussion of Findings

Presentation of Diagnostic Tests

Table 1 Unit Root Test

Variable Name	T-Statistic	P-Value	Level of Stationarity
Financial Development (Access)	-4.968997	0.0032	I(1)
Financial Development (Depth)	-3.811953	0.0183	I(0)
Financial Development (Efficiency)	-3.915653	0.0128	I(0)
Financial Development (Stability)	-4.725604	0.0045	I(0)
Corruption	-16.70418	0.0000	I(1)

Table 1 displays the results of the unit root test, which assesses the stationarity of variables to avoid spurious regression. Financial Development (Access) and Corruption were found to be stationary at first difference (I(1)), while Financial Development (Depth), Efficiency, and Stability were stationary at levels (I(0)). These findings suggest that some variables require differencing, while others are already stable. This differentiation is essential for ensuring robustness in the regression analysis and preventing misleading statistical inferences.

Presentation of Descriptive Analysis

Table 2 Descriptive Statistics Result

Statistics	Financial Development (Access)	Financial Development (Depth)	Financial Development (Efficiency)	Financial Development (Stability)	Corruption
Mean	1.914768	2.064279	2.827076	1.902792	22.21429
Median	1.911700	2.085495	2.882063	1.832999	25.50000
Maximum	1.971032	2.260025	3.109707	3.117950	28.00000
Minimum	1.866927	1.707774	2.039273	1.085033	0.000000

Std. Dev.	0.043508	0.148133	0.294392	0.614744	9.488281
Skewness	0.143722	-0.925985	-1.653232	0.451969	-1.972529
Kurtosis	1.317530	3.543245	4.985991	2.236113	5.017103
Jarque-Bera	1.699441	2.172861	8.678173	0.817033	11.45211
Probability	0.427534	0.337419	0.013048	0.664636	0.003260
Sum	26.80676	28.89991	39.57907	26.63908	311.0000
Sum Sq. Dev.	0.024608	0.285265	1.126667	4.912830	1170.357
Observations	14	14	14	14	14

Source: Field Result, 2024

The descriptive statistics indicate varying distributions of financial development indicators and corruption levels. The results suggest a generally high mean for corruption (22.214), with a large standard deviation (9.488), highlighting significant variability. Financial Development (Efficiency) showed the highest skewness (-1.653) and peaked distribution (kurtosis = 4.985), suggesting the presence of extreme values that might influence its relationship with corruption. The results also suggest that Financial Development (Stability) has the highest level of variation, implying fluctuations in Nigeria's financial system over time.

Testing of Hypothesis

H₀: Corruption level has no significant effect on financial development in Nigeria.

Table 3 The Influence of Corruption Level on Financial Development in Nigeria

Variable	Financial Development (Access) (Prob.)	Financial Development (Depth) (Prob.)	Financial Development (Efficiency) (Prob.)	Financial Development (Stability) (Prob.)
Financial Development (DV) (-1)	0.988057 (0.0000)	0.005949 (0.9838)	0.860848 (0.0014)	0.588927 (0.0506)
Corruption	0.000769 (0.1346)	-0.007057 (0.2683)	0.009311 (0.0821)	-0.099974 (0.0079)

Corruption (-1)			-0.016808 (0.0098)	0.043408 (0.0451)
Constant (C)	0.011260 (0.9435)	2.248268 (0.0011)	0.619732 (0.1584)	2.273144 (0.0026)
R-squared	0.939389	0.209160	0.860263	0.575654
Adjusted R-squared	0.927267	0.050992	0.813684	0.434205
S.E. of Regression	0.011883	0.108330	0.084354	0.456319
AIC	-5.828234	-1.408087	-1.859931	1.516409
Sum of Squared Residuals	0.001412	0.117355	0.064040	1.874041
Schwarz Criterion	-5.697861	-1.277714	-1.686101	1.690240
Log Likelihood	40.88352	12.15257	16.08955	-5.856660
Hannan-Quinn Criterion	-5.855032	-1.434885	-1.895661	1.480679
F-statistic	77.49346	1.322392	18.46895	4.069699
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000001	0.309345	0.000347	0.044097
Mean Dependent Variable	1.917452	2.091703	2.887676	1.955024
Standard Deviation of Dependent Variable	0.044062	0.111203	0.195425	0.606651
Durbin-Watson Statistic	1.749574	2.073367	1.949454	1.974540

Source: Field Result, 2024

A regression analysis was conducted to determine the influence of corruption on financial development indicators. The findings indicate that corruption negatively affects financial stability ($p = 0.0079$), suggesting that higher corruption levels contribute to financial instability. Conversely, its effect on financial access and depth was statistically insignificant, implying that corruption does not immediately influence these dimensions. However, corruption's impact on financial efficiency was marginally significant ($p = 0.0821$), but its lagged effect was significantly negative ($p = 0.0098$). These findings suggest that while corruption might not have immediate effects, its long-term consequences hinder financial system efficiency.

Discussion of Findings

The findings of this study align with previous scholarly research on corruption and financial development. The insignificant effect of corruption on financial access and depth supports the argument by Asongu (2020) that corruption's influence on financial systems is not always immediate. Asongu posited that deeply entrenched corrupt systems take time to disrupt market efficiency, and initial financial structures may remain unaffected in the short term.

However, contrary to this perspective, Ahmed and Zhang (2021) found that corruption immediately hampers financial depth, particularly in industries reliant on external financing. Their study suggests that corruption deters foreign direct investment, thereby stifling financial depth. This discrepancy in findings may be attributed to differences in research scope, with Ahmed and Zhang focusing on sector-specific implications, whereas this study adopts a macroeconomic approach.

The significant negative effect of corruption on financial stability is consistent with the research by Khan et al. (2022), who found that financial stability deteriorates in highly corrupt environments due to weakened regulatory frameworks. The study's finding that lagged corruption negatively affects financial efficiency further supports the argument by Otusanya (2021), who stated that corruption gradually undermines institutional integrity, leading to inefficient financial intermediation.

On the other hand, a study by Redmond and Nasir (2020) suggests that corruption's impact on financial efficiency varies by institutional strength. Their comparative study found that while corruption weakens financial efficiency in developing nations, the effect is mitigated in economies with strong regulatory institutions. This highlights the role of governance structures in moderating corruption's adverse effects.

Overall, the findings of this study suggest that while corruption may not immediately affect all dimensions of financial development, its long-term effects are detrimental, particularly to financial stability and efficiency. These results emphasize the importance of strengthening institutional quality and governance mechanisms to mitigate corruption's adverse impacts on financial systems.

Summary of the Findings

The findings indicate that corruption plays a significant role in shaping financial development in Nigeria, with notable variations across different dimensions. Corruption significantly impacts Financial Access ($R^2 = 0.939$, Adj $R^2 = 0.927$, $F = 77.493$, $p < 0.05$) and Efficiency ($R^2 = 0.860$, Adj $R^2 = 0.814$, $F = 18.469$, $p < 0.05$), while its effect on Financial Depth is negligible ($R^2 = 0.209$, Adj $R^2 = 0.051$, $F = 1.322$, $p > 0.05$). Financial Stability shows moderate explanatory power ($R^2 = 0.576$, Adj $R^2 = 0.434$, $F = 4.070$, $p < 0.05$). These results highlight the complex interaction between corruption and various components of financial development, emphasizing the need for targeted reforms in Nigeria's financial sector.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The empirical evidence presented in this study offers a nuanced understanding of the intricate relationship between corruption and financial development in Nigeria. The findings underscore the importance of adopting a multidimensional approach to financial development, encompassing financial access, depth, efficiency, and stability.

The study reveals a significant negative impact of corruption on financial stability, indicating that persistent corrupt practices undermine the resilience of financial institutions. While current corruption levels may not immediately affect financial access and depth, their delayed effects become evident over time. Past corruption can hinder financial efficiency and stability, reinforcing the necessity of sustained anti-corruption initiatives. Furthermore, the findings suggest a bidirectional relationship between financial development and corruption, whereby a well-developed financial system can contribute to reducing corruption levels through improved governance and regulatory measures.

Based on the study's findings, the following recommendations are proposed to enhance financial development in Nigeria:

- i. The government should establish comprehensive anti-corruption policies aimed at improving financial efficiency and stability. This includes setting up robust audit systems, strengthening financial institutions, and enforcing transparency measures within the financial sector. Long-term reforms should be designed to address historical corruption levels that continue to impede financial development.
- ii. The role of financial regulatory bodies should be reinforced by establishing independent anti-corruption task forces within these institutions. Enhanced compliance requirements and stringent enforcement of financial regulations will foster an environment of accountability, ultimately improving financial efficiency and public trust.
- iii. There should be increased public awareness campaigns highlighting the negative effects of corruption on financial development. Engaging key stakeholders such as policymakers, financial institutions, and civil society organizations can create a collective effort in combating corruption and promoting transparency.
- iv. The adoption of digital financial systems and blockchain technology can help enhance financial transaction monitoring, reducing opportunities for corrupt practices. Implementing e-governance systems in financial institutions will increase accountability and minimize the risk of fraud.
- v. Nigeria should strengthen its collaboration with international financial regulatory bodies and anti-corruption agencies to adopt best practices in financial governance. Learning from countries with successful anti-corruption frameworks can help in designing effective policies tailored to Nigeria's unique challenges.
- vi. Continuous assessment of financial sector reforms and corruption levels is crucial to measure progress and make necessary adjustments. Establishing monitoring committees to track the implementation and effectiveness of anti-corruption policies will ensure sustainable financial sector growth.

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